

Supplementary Material A

Satellite band-site richness analysis

The raw count of species richness at each site was graphed against satellite band information (Fig. S.1.1). Band data for each site was calculated as the mean value across a circle with a 3km diameter centred on the survey start spot. Based upon these graphs, band 4 correlated the strongest with the raw number of species detected at each site. Indices assessed were Normalised Difference Sand Dune Index (NDSDI), Normalised Difference Sand Index (NDSI), Dry Bare Sand Index (DBSI), Normalised Difference Sandy Land Index (NDSLII), Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) and the Normalised Difference Enhanced Sand Index (NDESI; Marzouki and Dridri 2022).

Fig. S.1.1: The relationships examined between the satellite bands (and combinations) and the raw number of species detected at each site.

To capture the level of complexity, the coefficient of variation in band 4 reflectance across each circled area was calculated and combined with band 12 in Equation (S.1; also refer to Fig. S.1.2):

$$\text{Eq. (S.1): THI} = (\text{CV}_{\text{band4}} - \text{band 12}) / (\text{CV}_{\text{band4}} + \text{band 12})$$

A map of THI calculated across 1km grids is provided in Fig. S.1.3.

Fig. S.1. 2: Relationship between Topographic Heterogeneity Index (THI) and the raw number of species detected at each site.

Fig. S.1.3: Topographic Heterogeneity Index across the study area. Size of each study site marker is scaled by the number of species detected. Note, index is calculated over an area of 1 km².

Supplementary Material B

Statistical information

Occupancy and detection formulas

```
occ.ms.sp.formula.nc <- ~ 1
occ.ms.sp.formula <- ~ scale(THI)
det.ms.sp.formula.nc <- ~ 1
det.ms.sp.formula.1 <- ~ scale (day)
det.ms.sp.formula.2 <- ~ scale (THI)
det.ms.sp.formula.3 <- ~ scale (day+ THI)
```

Preferred model (no spatial autocorrelation) outputs

Samples per Chain: 100000

Burn-in: 20000

Thinning Rate: 100

Number of Chains: 3

Total Posterior Samples: 2400

Community Level

Occurrence Means (logit scale)							
	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
Intercept	0.36	1.05	-1.06	0.14	3.10	1.00	724
scaled (THI)	1.00	0.84	-1.02	1.07	2.52	1.00	875
Occurrence Variances (logit scale)							
	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
Intercept	2.32	2.36	0.13	1.68	8.49	1.01	1875
scaled (THI)	0.74	1.88	0.04	0.26	4.32	1.03	1615
Detection Means (logit scale)							
	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
Intercept	0.30	0.88	-1.17	0.22	2.16	1.00	864
scaled (day since start of survey)	-0.14	0.47	-1.16	-0.14	0.77	1.00	2400
scaled (THI)	-0.26	0.72	-1.66	-0.26	1.09	1.00	926
Detection Variances (logit scale)							
	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
Intercept	2.49	2.92	0.14	1.74	9.29	1.02	2243
scaled (day since start of survey)	2.65	4.94	0.08	1.18	14.63	1.02	1631
scaled (THI)	0.63	1.06	0.04	0.29	3.22	1.02	1931

Species Level

Occurrence (logit scale)

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
(Intercept)- <i>Acanthodactylus boskianus</i>	-0.64	1.71	-3.42	-0.93	3.47	1.00	1187
(Intercept)- <i>Acanthodactylus opheodurus</i>	0.38	1.57	-1.97	0.11	4.15	1.00	1045
(Intercept)- <i>Acanthodactylus schmidtii</i>	-0.32	1.74	-3.21	-0.53	3.60	1.00	976
(Intercept)- <i>Bunopus tuberculatus</i>	-0.29	1.64	-2.80	-0.66	3.65	1.00	959
(Intercept)- <i>Cerastes gasperetti</i>	-0.70	1.72	-3.63	-0.96	3.32	1.01	1041
(Intercept)- <i>Eryx jayakari</i>	-0.23	1.74	-3.07	-0.49	3.64	1.00	1158
(Intercept)- <i>Mesalina brevirostris</i>	-0.18	1.78	-3.09	-0.40	3.70	1.00	1092
(Intercept)- <i>Phrynocephalus arabicus</i>	0.59	1.38	-1.15	0.30	4.20	1.01	1205
(Intercept)- <i>Platyceps rhodorachis</i>	-0.29	1.74	-3.15	-0.49	3.56	1.00	944
(Intercept)- <i>Pristurus minimus</i>	0.68	1.37	-1.32	0.45	3.91	1.00	1128
(Intercept)- <i>Pseudotrapelus sinaitus</i>	0.41	1.56	-2.09	0.24	3.98	1.02	1059
(Intercept)- <i>Ptyodactylus hasselquistii</i>	0.22	1.56	-2.17	-0.03	3.72	1.00	1175
(Intercept)- <i>Scincus mitranus</i>	0.52	1.54	-1.63	0.23	4.23	1.00	826
(Intercept)- <i>Stenodactylus doriae</i>	1.97	1.31	0.12	1.76	5.23	1.01	1492
(Intercept)- <i>Stenodactylus slevini</i>	1.02	1.24	-0.82	0.83	4.12	1.00	1293
(Intercept)- <i>Trigonodactylus arabicus</i>	1.42	1.31	-0.41	1.18	4.69	1.00	1191
(Intercept)- <i>Uromastix aegyptia</i>	2.13	1.41	0.19	1.86	5.63	1.00	1918
(Intercept)- <i>Varanus griseus</i>	0.39	1.63	-1.95	0.08	4.15	1.01	966
scaled(THI)- <i>Acanthodactylus boskianus</i>	0.97	1.26	-1.82	1.02	3.31	1.01	1158
scaled(THI)- <i>Acanthodactylus opheodurus</i>	1.20	1.06	-1.00	1.17	3.49	1.01	1545
scaled(THI)- <i>Acanthodactylus schmidtii</i>	0.99	1.25	-1.82	1.02	3.47	1.00	1051
scaled(THI)- <i>Bunopus tuberculatus</i>	1.05	1.04	-1.10	1.06	3.19	1.00	1342
scaled(THI)- <i>Cerastes gasperetti</i>	0.97	1.19	-1.64	1.02	3.16	1.01	1254
scaled(THI)- <i>Eryx jayakari</i>	1.04	1.23	-1.62	1.08	3.42	1.00	1131
scaled(THI)- <i>Mesalina brevirostris</i>	0.81	1.28	-2.00	0.90	3.09	1.00	1100
scaled(THI)- <i>Phrynocephalus arabicus</i>	0.79	0.86	-1.21	0.85	2.41	1.00	1242
scaled(THI)- <i>Platyceps rhodorachis</i>	1.00	1.19	-1.49	1.04	3.33	1.00	1188
scaled(THI)- <i>Pristurus minimus</i>	1.09	1.29	-1.82	1.15	3.63	1.00	1192
scaled(THI)- <i>Pseudotrapelus sinaitus</i>	0.82	1.13	-1.84	0.93	2.74	1.00	1075
scaled(THI)- <i>Ptyodactylus hasselquistii</i>	0.87	1.24	-1.83	0.93	3.25	1.00	1223
scaled(THI)- <i>Scincus mitranus</i>	1.30	1.12	-0.93	1.27	3.74	1.01	1291
scaled(THI)- <i>Stenodactylus doriae</i>	1.14	0.97	-0.90	1.13	3.13	1.00	1083
scaled(THI)- <i>Stenodactylus slevini</i>	1.28	1.22	-1.40	1.31	3.81	1.01	1288
scaled(THI)- <i>Trigonodactylus arabicus</i>	1.00	0.95	-1.18	1.04	2.91	1.00	1069
scaled(THI)- <i>Uromastix aegyptia</i>	0.85	0.84	-1.04	0.90	2.47	1.00	1169
scaled(THI)- <i>Varanus griseus</i>	1.12	1.10	-1.10	1.09	3.48	1.01	1274

Detection (logit scale)

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus boskianus	0.48	1.74	-2.38	0.31	4.50	1.00	1413
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	-0.03	1.40	-2.48	-0.13	2.89	1.01	1473
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus schmidtii	-0.70	1.50	-3.40	-0.81	2.30	1.00	1958
(Intercept)-Bunopus tuberculatus	0.55	1.75	-2.08	0.37	4.41	1.02	1385
(Intercept)-Cerastes gasperetti	0.51	1.78	-2.29	0.33	4.63	1.01	1256
(Intercept)-Eryx jayakari	-0.74	1.52	-3.60	-0.84	2.33	1.01	1795
(Intercept)-Mesalina brevirostris	-0.57	1.74	-3.71	-0.75	3.10	1.00	1642
(Intercept)-Phrynocephalus arabicus	1.57	1.72	-0.83	1.28	5.89	1.00	1426
(Intercept)-Platyceps rhodorachis	-0.71	1.55	-3.52	-0.82	2.45	1.00	1621
(Intercept)-Pristurus minimus	0.71	1.12	-1.13	0.60	3.19	1.00	1349
(Intercept)-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	-0.55	1.35	-3.01	-0.68	2.27	1.00	1549
(Intercept)-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	-0.37	1.36	-2.82	-0.50	2.46	1.00	1527
(Intercept)-Scincus mitranus	0.36	1.25	-1.70	0.19	3.05	1.01	1284
(Intercept)-Stenodactylus doriae	2.50	1.47	0.52	2.23	6.26	1.00	1850
(Intercept)-Stenodactylus slevini	0.59	1.08	-1.14	0.47	2.92	1.01	1299
(Intercept)-Trigonodactylus arabicus	0.95	1.09	-0.74	0.81	3.45	1.01	1484
(Intercept)-Uromastix aegyptia	1.24	0.80	-0.10	1.17	2.96	1.00	1942
(Intercept)-Varanus griseus	0.04	1.38	-2.16	-0.13	2.96	1.00	1510
scaled(day since start of survey)-Acanthodactylus boskianus	0.02	1.07	-2.24	-0.01	2.32	1.01	2400
scaled(day since start of survey)-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	-1.75	1.56	-5.61	-1.41	0.15	1.00	1563
scaled(day since start of survey)-Acanthodactylus schmidtii	-1.00	1.55	-5.00	-0.65	0.83	1.01	1573
scaled(day since start of survey)-Bunopus tuberculatus	-1.14	1.63	-5.51	-0.79	1.12	1.00	2064
scaled(day since start of survey)-Cerastes gasperetti	0.02	1.09	-2.21	0.02	2.35	1.00	2400
scaled(day since start of survey)-Eryx jayakari	0.98	1.43	-0.85	0.66	4.80	1.00	1919
scaled(day since start of survey)-Mesalina brevirostris	-0.68	1.36	-3.99	-0.50	1.62	1.01	2499
scaled(day since start of survey)-Phrynocephalus arabicus	-0.35	0.98	-2.49	-0.30	1.62	1.00	2210
scaled(day since start of survey)-Platyceps rhodorachis	-1.02	1.48	-5.01	-0.70	0.84	1.00	2032
scaled(day since start of survey)-Pristurus minimus	0.35	0.91	-1.09	0.23	2.53	1.01	2085
scaled(day since start of survey)-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	1.23	1.49	-0.50	0.88	4.86	1.01	1906
scaled(day since start of survey)-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	-1.10	1.52	-4.68	-0.73	0.74	1.01	2052
scaled(day since start of survey)-Scincus mitranus	0.45	0.83	-0.90	0.31	2.47	1.00	2009
scaled(day since start of survey)-Stenodactylus doriae	-0.33	0.91	-2.24	-0.30	1.56	1.00	2383
scaled(day since start of survey)-Stenodactylus slevini	1.60	1.46	-0.29	1.32	5.35	1.01	1189
scaled(day since start of survey)-Trigonodactylus arabicus	0.49	0.89	-0.88	0.35	2.69	1.00	1993
scaled(day since start of survey)-Uromastix aegyptia	-0.21	0.63	-1.52	-0.21	1.06	1.00	2400
scaled(day since start of survey)-Varanus griseus	-0.40	1.15	-2.73	-0.38	1.98	1.00	2400
scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus boskianus	-0.21	1.14	-2.50	-0.19	1.94	1.00	1445
scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	0.04	0.94	-1.84	0.05	1.83	1.00	1159
scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus schmidtii	-0.39	1.07	-2.80	-0.33	1.52	1.01	1124
scaled(THI)-Bunopus tuberculatus	0.01	0.97	-1.92	0.02	1.90	1.00	1385
scaled(THI)-Cerastes gasperetti	-0.13	1.06	-2.16	-0.12	1.92	1.00	1291
scaled(THI)-Eryx jayakari	-0.33	1.07	-2.68	-0.27	1.56	1.00	1435

scaled(THI)- <i>Mesalina brevisrostris</i>	-0.45	1.12	-2.87	-0.37	1.50	1.00	1618
scaled(THI)- <i>Phrynocephalus arabicus</i>	-0.06	0.80	-1.71	-0.05	1.43	1.01	1592
scaled(THI)- <i>Platyceps rhodorachis</i>	-0.36	1.07	-2.76	-0.28	1.54	1.00	1385
scaled(THI)- <i>Pristurus minimus</i>	-0.51	1.11	-3.02	-0.44	1.47	1.00	976
scaled(THI)- <i>Pseudotrapelus sinaitus</i>	-0.45	1.04	-2.79	-0.38	1.28	1.00	1393
scaled(THI)- <i>Ptyodactylus hasselquistii</i>	-0.50	1.11	-3.07	-0.42	1.38	1.00	1166
scaled(THI)- <i>Scincus mitranus</i>	-0.09	0.85	-1.80	-0.07	1.53	1.00	1394
scaled(THI)- <i>Stenodactylus doriae</i>	0.04	0.90	-1.74	0.05	1.73	1.00	1435
scaled(THI)- <i>Stenodactylus slevini</i>	-0.48	1.05	-2.71	-0.41	1.34	1.00	1110
scaled(THI)- <i>Trigonodactylus arabicus</i>	-0.36	0.82	-2.12	-0.34	1.08	1.01	1357
scaled(THI)- <i>Uromastix aegyptia</i>	-0.22	0.70	-1.75	-0.20	1.11	1.01	957
scaled(THI)- <i>Varanus griseus</i>	-0.39	0.91	-2.37	-0.32	1.19	1.00	891

Posterior predictive checks

Community Level

Bayesian p-value: 0.40

Species Level

<i>Acanthodactylus boskianus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.19
<i>Acanthodactylus opheodurus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.46
<i>Acanthodactylus schmidti</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.45
<i>Bunopus tuberculatus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.24
<i>Cerastes gasperetti</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.21
<i>Eryx jayakari</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.46
<i>Mesalina brevisrostris</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.34
<i>Phrynocephalus arabicus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.23
<i>Platyceps rhodorachis</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.47
<i>Pristurus minimus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.36
<i>Pseudotrapelus sinaitus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.48
<i>Ptyodactylus hasselquistii</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.44
<i>Scincus mitranus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.41
<i>Stenodactylus doriae</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.54
<i>Stenodactylus slevini</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.58
<i>Trigonodactylus arabicus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.42
<i>Uromastix aegyptia</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.46
<i>Varanus griseus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.38

Preferred model (spatial autocorrelation) outputs

Samples per Chain: 100000

Burn-in: 2000

Thinning Rate: 20

Number of Chains: 3

Total Posterior Samples: 14700

Community Level

Occurrence Means (logit scale)

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
Intercept	0.21	1.03	-1.38	0.03	2.69	1.00	1427
scaled (THI)	1.23	0.83	-0.80	1.28	2.75	1.00	1467

Occurrence Variances (logit scale)

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
Intercept	3.04	3.29	0.15	2.21	11.07	1.00	5630
scaled (THI)	0.77	1.93	0.04	0.30	4.23	1.01	3656

Detection Means (logit scale)

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
Intercept	0.42	0.87	-1.06	0.36	2.28	1.00	1763
scaled (day since start of survey)	-0.14	0.49	-1.21	-0.13	0.83	1.00	14199
scaled (THI)	-0.32	0.69	-1.71	-0.32	1.00	1.00	1554

Detection Variances (logit scale)

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
Intercept	2.61	2.83	0.14	1.79	10.10	1.00	7196
scaled (day since start of survey)	3.05	5.35	0.09	1.35	16.18	1.00	3236
scaled (THI)	0.67	1.43	0.04	0.29	3.61	1.01	7603

Species Level

Occurrence (logit scale)

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus boskianus	-0.98	1.79	-4.09	-1.16	2.91	1.00	2535
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	0.20	1.68	-2.46	-0.05	4.15	1.00	2550
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus schmidti	-0.54	1.87	-3.83	-0.69	3.57	1.00	2452
(Intercept)-Bunopus tuberculatus	-0.52	1.71	-3.25	-0.74	3.46	1.00	2144
(Intercept)-Cerastes gasperetti	-1.05	1.79	-4.17	-1.23	2.95	1.00	2144
(Intercept)-Eryx jayakari	-0.49	1.82	-3.72	-0.63	3.46	1.00	2507
(Intercept)-Mesalina brevirostris	-0.46	1.87	-3.77	-0.61	3.51	1.00	2719
(Intercept)-Phrynocephalus arabicus	0.53	1.45	-1.59	0.30	4.10	1.00	2806
(Intercept)-Platyceps rhodorachis	-0.54	1.87	-3.86	-0.69	3.50	1.00	2624
(Intercept)-Pristurus minimus	0.53	1.45	-1.77	0.34	3.86	1.00	2847
(Intercept)-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	0.24	1.74	-2.60	0.03	4.14	1.00	2741
(Intercept)-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	0.02	1.69	-2.79	-0.17	3.75	1.00	2753
(Intercept)-Scincus mitranus	0.34	1.59	-2.10	0.11	4.12	1.00	2193
(Intercept)-Stenodactylus doriae	2.02	1.44	-0.17	1.82	5.45	1.00	3870
(Intercept)-Stenodactylus slevini	1.00	1.33	-1.11	0.84	4.15	1.00	2898
(Intercept)-Trigonodactylus arabicus	1.36	1.47	-0.81	1.13	4.93	1.00	3313
(Intercept)-Uromastix aegyptia	2.27	1.57	-0.07	2.03	6.03	1.00	5574
(Intercept)-Varanus griseus	0.17	1.67	-2.43	-0.06	4.08	1.00	2357
scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus boskianus	1.19	1.24	-1.42	1.22	3.54	1.00	2137

scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	1.40	1.10	-0.81	1.38	3.64	1.00	2746
scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus schmidti	1.23	1.25	-1.40	1.24	3.63	1.00	2445
scaled(THI)-Bunopus tuberculatus	1.24	1.02	-0.90	1.25	3.22	1.00	2573
scaled(THI)-Cerastes gasperetti	1.22	1.18	-1.26	1.23	3.48	1.00	2267
scaled(THI)-Eryx jayakari	1.30	1.24	-1.30	1.32	3.74	1.00	2394
scaled(THI)-Mesalina brevirostris	1.04	1.29	-1.75	1.11	3.35	1.00	2238
scaled(THI)-Phrynocephalus arabicus	1.02	0.91	-0.98	1.07	2.72	1.00	2305
scaled(THI)-Platyceps rhodorachis	1.22	1.25	-1.44	1.24	3.63	1.00	2319
scaled(THI)-Pristurus minimus	1.34	1.26	-1.37	1.36	3.82	1.00	2108
scaled(THI)-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	1.06	1.16	-1.57	1.14	3.18	1.00	2252
scaled(THI)-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	1.11	1.25	-1.64	1.17	3.40	1.00	2216
scaled(THI)-Scincus mitranus	1.53	1.13	-0.73	1.50	3.88	1.00	2822
scaled(THI)-Stenodactylus doriae	1.37	1.01	-0.80	1.38	3.40	1.00	2569
scaled(THI)-Stenodactylus slevini	1.54	1.20	-1.03	1.52	4.03	1.00	2271
scaled(THI)-Trigonodactylus arabicus	1.24	0.97	-0.91	1.27	3.16	1.00	2588
scaled(THI)-Uromastix aegyptia	1.08	0.91	-0.92	1.12	2.80	1.00	2842
scaled(THI)-Varanus griseus	1.31	1.09	-0.88	1.30	3.49	1.00	2737

Detection (logit scale)

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus boskianus	0.64	1.73	-2.17	0.48	4.58	1.00	2724
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	0.11	1.38	-2.37	0.01	2.97	1.00	3844
(Intercept)-Acanthodactylus schmidti	-0.64	1.57	-3.53	-0.71	2.51	1.00	3509
(Intercept)-Bunopus tuberculatus	0.72	1.71	-2.05	0.55	4.65	1.00	3237
(Intercept)-Cerastes gasperetti	0.71	1.79	-2.24	0.56	4.82	1.00	2888
(Intercept)-Eryx jayakari	-0.60	1.53	-3.47	-0.68	2.45	1.00	3587
(Intercept)-Mesalina brevirostris	-0.44	1.79	-3.66	-0.59	3.21	1.00	4651
(Intercept)-Phrynocephalus arabicus	1.77	1.69	-0.73	1.52	5.79	1.00	3353
(Intercept)-Platyceps rhodorachis	-0.64	1.57	-3.57	-0.73	2.52	1.00	3964
(Intercept)-Pristurus minimus	0.84	1.20	-1.06	0.68	3.61	1.00	3024
(Intercept)-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	-0.49	1.38	-3.01	-0.58	2.39	1.00	4386
(Intercept)-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	-0.26	1.36	-2.66	-0.36	2.62	1.00	3957
(Intercept)-Scincus mitranus	0.49	1.29	-1.60	0.35	3.36	1.00	2397
(Intercept)-Stenodactylus doriae	2.63	1.51	0.51	2.35	6.32	1.00	3960
(Intercept)-Stenodactylus slevini	0.66	1.09	-1.16	0.56	3.11	1.00	2823
(Intercept)-Trigonodactylus arabicus	1.10	1.11	-0.63	0.95	3.72	1.00	3679
(Intercept)-Uromastix aegyptia	1.31	0.80	-0.07	1.23	3.09	1.00	4516
(Intercept)-Varanus griseus	0.24	1.40	-2.07	0.09	3.31	1.00	2995
scaled(day since start of survey)-Acanthodactylus boskianus	0.03	1.15	-2.34	0.01	2.45	1.00	14700
scaled(day since start of survey)-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	-1.89	1.66	-6.18	-1.51	0.14	1.00	3715
scaled(day since start of survey)-Acanthodactylus schmidti	-1.12	1.60	-5.49	-0.74	0.85	1.00	4446
scaled(day since start of survey)-Bunopus tuberculatus	-1.21	1.72	-5.72	-0.84	1.12	1.00	5461
scaled(day since start of survey)-Cerastes gasperetti	0.04	1.13	-2.30	0.03	2.44	1.00	14700
scaled(day since start of survey)-Eryx jayakari	1.12	1.64	-0.88	0.74	5.40	1.00	3809
scaled(day since start of survey)-Mesalina brevirostris	-0.76	1.46	-4.41	-0.52	1.48	1.00	9363
scaled(day since start of survey)-Phrynocephalus arabicus	-0.35	1.00	-2.52	-0.31	1.57	1.00	14015
scaled(day since start of survey)-Platyceps rhodorachis	-1.10	1.60	-5.22	-0.73	0.85	1.00	4466
scaled(day since start of survey)-Pristurus minimus	0.42	0.95	-1.09	0.28	2.80	1.00	5304
scaled(day since start of survey)-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	1.33	1.63	-0.57	0.94	5.65	1.00	3693
scaled(day since start of survey)-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	-1.22	1.63	-5.62	-0.81	0.74	1.00	5186
scaled(day since start of survey)-Scincus mitranus	0.51	0.90	-0.87	0.37	2.69	1.00	5425
scaled(day since start of survey)-Stenodactylus doriae	-0.34	0.94	-2.33	-0.30	1.52	1.00	14700
scaled(day since start of survey)-Stenodactylus slevini	1.74	1.58	-0.26	1.39	5.70	1.00	2831
scaled(day since start of survey)-Trigonodactylus arabicus	0.59	0.94	-0.81	0.42	2.88	1.00	6394
scaled(day since start of survey)-Uromastix aegyptia	-0.24	0.66	-1.62	-0.22	1.03	1.00	12613
scaled(day since start of survey)-Varanus griseus	-0.37	1.22	-2.86	-0.35	2.32	1.00	12952
scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus boskianus	-0.30	1.12	-2.62	-0.28	1.78	1.00	3320
scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	-0.03	0.93	-1.90	-0.03	1.76	1.00	3245
scaled(THI)-Acanthodactylus schmidti	-0.42	1.10	-2.83	-0.34	1.48	1.00	3091
scaled(THI)-Bunopus tuberculatus	-0.05	0.95	-1.89	-0.06	1.82	1.00	3400
scaled(THI)-Cerastes gasperetti	-0.17	1.10	-2.34	-0.18	1.98	1.00	3594
scaled(THI)-Eryx jayakari	-0.40	1.09	-2.80	-0.32	1.44	1.00	2786

scaled(THI)-Mesalina brevirostris	-0.54	1.14	-3.09	-0.45	1.32	1.00	2812
scaled(THI)-Phrynocephalus arabicus	-0.13	0.81	-1.79	-0.11	1.40	1.00	3372
scaled(THI)-Platyceps rhodorachis	-0.42	1.11	-2.89	-0.34	1.47	1.00	2782
scaled(THI)-Pristurus minimus	-0.58	1.10	-3.05	-0.50	1.33	1.00	2179
scaled(THI)-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	-0.52	1.05	-2.86	-0.42	1.21	1.00	2774
scaled(THI)-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	-0.57	1.12	-3.17	-0.47	1.29	1.00	2461
scaled(THI)-Scincus mitranus	-0.17	0.86	-1.93	-0.15	1.46	1.00	2510
scaled(THI)-Stenodactylus doriae	-0.02	0.87	-1.70	-0.03	1.68	1.00	3674
scaled(THI)-Stenodactylus slevini	-0.54	1.02	-2.79	-0.48	1.23	1.00	2255
scaled(THI)-Trigonodactylus arabicus	-0.40	0.79	-2.09	-0.36	1.02	1.00	2685
scaled(THI)-Uromastix aegyptia	-0.28	0.70	-1.77	-0.25	1.02	1.00	2617
scaled(THI)-Varanus griseus	-0.43	0.91	-2.44	-0.37	1.14	1.00	2344

Spatial Covariance

	Mean	SD	2.50%	50%	97.50%	Rhat	ESS
sigma.sq-Acanthodactylus boskianus	1.91	3.70	0.36	1.18	7.49	1.02	12562
sigma.sq-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	2.01	5.52	0.37	1.20	8.03	1.19	8739
sigma.sq-Acanthodactylus schmidti	1.98	4.33	0.36	1.19	7.91	1.02	10941
sigma.sq-Bunopus tuberculatus	2.11	4.48	0.36	1.24	8.94	1.09	13316
sigma.sq-Cerastes gasperetti	1.94	3.93	0.36	1.18	7.93	1.12	12758
sigma.sq-Eryx jayakari	1.86	2.97	0.35	1.17	7.37	1.00	14013
sigma.sq-Mesalina brevirostris	2.15	6.47	0.36	1.20	8.97	1.09	13276
sigma.sq-Phrynocephalus arabicus	2.85	11.59	0.38	1.38	13.37	1.20	8336
sigma.sq-Platyceps rhodorachis	1.93	3.16	0.36	1.18	7.65	1.01	13329
sigma.sq-Pristurus minimus	2.07	3.74	0.36	1.21	8.99	1.02	10776
sigma.sq-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	2.17	3.99	0.37	1.25	9.30	1.04	11366
sigma.sq-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	2.21	4.85	0.36	1.26	9.51	1.00	9852
sigma.sq-Scincus mitranus	1.84	3.01	0.36	1.18	7.27	1.01	12084
sigma.sq-Stenodactylus doriae	1.75	2.74	0.34	1.12	6.84	1.02	13581
sigma.sq-Stenodactylus slevini	1.68	2.17	0.35	1.12	6.62	1.00	14199
sigma.sq-Trigonodactylus arabicus	2.10	3.61	0.37	1.25	8.97	1.00	12466
sigma.sq-Uromastix aegyptia	1.75	2.11	0.35	1.15	6.94	1.00	13568
sigma.sq-Varanus griseus	2.16	3.63	0.37	1.27	9.49	1.01	13018
phi-Acanthodactylus boskianus	10.00	4.27	2.96	10.00	17.04	1.00	14700
phi-Acanthodactylus opheodurus	9.95	4.27	2.99	9.90	17.04	1.00	14700
phi-Acanthodactylus schmidti	10.05	4.28	2.99	10.05	17.06	1.00	14700
phi-Bunopus tuberculatus	10.05	4.27	3.00	10.04	17.06	1.00	14242
phi-Cerastes gasperetti	9.94	4.28	2.96	9.88	17.03	1.00	15895
phi-Eryx jayakari	10.04	4.27	2.98	10.06	17.05	1.00	14127
phi-Mesalina brevirostris	10.16	4.25	3.00	10.22	17.08	1.00	14359
phi-Phrynocephalus arabicus	10.24	4.25	3.04	10.33	17.07	1.00	14700
phi-Platyceps rhodorachis	9.98	4.27	3.01	9.97	17.06	1.00	14700
phi-Pristurus minimus	9.93	4.29	2.99	9.83	17.06	1.00	15118
phi-Pseudotrapelus sinaitus	10.08	4.26	2.97	10.09	17.07	1.00	14700
phi-Ptyodactylus hasselquistii	10.08	4.23	3.01	10.04	17.04	1.00	14700
phi-Scincus mitranus	9.94	4.27	2.98	9.95	17.03	1.00	14700
phi-Stenodactylus doriae	9.72	4.36	2.90	9.56	17.05	1.00	14700
phi-Stenodactylus slevini	10.01	4.25	2.99	10.06	17.01	1.00	14700
phi-Trigonodactylus arabicus	9.97	4.24	3.03	9.95	17.03	1.00	15110
phi-Uromastix aegyptia	9.92	4.31	2.97	9.83	17.06	1.00	14700
phi-Varanus griseus	9.91	4.29	2.94	9.89	17.02	1.00	14700

Posterior predictive checks

Community Level

Bayesian p-value: 0.43

Species Level

<i>Acanthodactylus boskianus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.51
<i>Acanthodactylus opheodurus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.47
<i>Acanthodactylus schmidtii</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.33
<i>Bunopus tuberculatus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.44
<i>Cerastes gasperetti</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.50
<i>Eryx jayakari</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.19
<i>Mesalina brevirostris</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.33
<i>Phrynocephalus arabicus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.41
<i>Platycephalus rhodorachis</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.33
<i>Pristurus minimus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.49
<i>Pseudotrapelus sinaitus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.46
<i>Ptyodactylus hasselquistii</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.32
<i>Scincus mitranus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.57
<i>Stenodactylus doriae</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.32
<i>Stenodactylus slevini</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.51
<i>Trigonodactylus arabicus</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.47
<i>Uromastix aegyptia</i>	Bayesian p-value	0.57